

Roman Mansio Above Žužemberk in Slovenia

While browsing DEM imagery of terrain, I noticed unusual features on the ground. Shape and dimensions indicated ruins of an unknown buildings. They are located 150 meters west of village Zgornji Cvibelj, above Žužemberk, Slovenija. A prominent location near the supposed ancient roman road and overlooking river Krka indicated the possible importance of the site.

Location

Žužemberk with its iconic medieval castle is a small town and center of upper Krka valley. Krka valley is a natural path connecting Ljubljana Basin with Panonia. All along the left bank of the river are known legends of ancient roman road. While modern road is positioned lower in the valley, closer to the river stream, legendary roman road was traced on the very upper edge of the valley. Such location would be logical as most prehistoric settlements are positioned on the karst plateau and hills along the Krka river. Zgornji Cvibelj is a small village positioned just above town Žužemberk, on the very edge of plateau. Pieces of roman pottery were found in the village. Some 150 meters from the last houses, west of the village is the location of observed ruins.

I traveled to the site and checked it on august 21st, 2020. A quick field survey was done with intention to clarify the nature of the buildings that stood here some time ago. Afternoon sun and good weather helped me in observing terrain features in detail.

Building A

A relatively young forest is covering terrain. Due to the vicinity of the village this forest was frequently cut. Light brown rendzina is covering the karstic subsurface limestone rock, which is penetrating the surface here and there. But generally soil depth is over 30 cm in most places. Large building (building A) ruin is positioned on a shallow saddle between two low heights. Short gravel road is connecting local (roman?) road with the east side of ruin. South east of ruin is some 8 meters deep dolina. Ruins are clearly visible in terrain as soil covered ridges with some stones protruding the surface. These ruins are on average 50 cm high, in some places higher and in some lower. One can easily follow the line of major walls. Terrain inside these walls is sort of leveled with a sort of terracing apparent. While soil in the wood is light brown rendzina with low clay content, soil inside ruins is much darker, almost black. A clear indicator of human presence. I found minute pieces of lime mortar near the walls. Despite careful observation I could not locate a single sherd

of pottery. But very small pieces of burnt soil or very eroded pottery are quite frequent. In the south western part of the building is a depression of 1m depth and some 2m radius. Dark muddy rain water collected in it. This is very strange for this karstic terrain with low clay presence. Depression could be up to 2m deep to my estimate. I assume these are remains of a rainwater cistern that collapsed, but still holds water on the lower side. Ruins of internal walls within building A are also clearly visible in terrain. One can recognize individual rooms, but not much detail apart from this. Building A is some 42 by 70 meters, oriented almost exactly north south direction on a longer axis.

Building B

36 meters from the south west corner of building A lies building B. This building is not so prominently expressed in terrain as former. More than ruins of assumed walls is a noticeable leveled area inside the building. Soil here is much lighter in color, in places of light brown color. No pottery or any other remains are to be found. But I noticed more versatility in color and smell of soil, going from black in one place to light brown, and even red in some spots. There also appears to me more forest undergrowth in this area. Building B is positioned on top of one of low height. Building is oriented NW-SE by a longer axis and is some 16 by 10 meters.

Building C

I could not recognize building C in terrain with some certainty. According to LIDAR imagery, size of the building is some 10 by 6 meters. Building is located halfway between building A and B and orientated in western esatern direction.

LIDAR data

DEM imagery I used is based on LIDAR data and has 1m horizontal resolution. Ruins of three buildings are clearly visible. Images 3, 4 and 5 present different views of DEM data. Interior walls in building A are clearly recognized in the DEM model. Building A consists of a large court surrounded by a strong wall and having an obvious entrance on the east side of the building, where the gravel road is still connecting the building with the main road. South part of the building was divided into 4 rooms of roughly equal size. Roughly in the middle of a spacious court is located an assumed rainwater cistern. Remains of walls around it suggest that it may have been inside some room or building. In the northern part of building A is a large building (some 20 by 12 meters) with visible internal divisions.

Maps and literature check

Maps from the 19th century do not show any building on this spot. Neither did I find any mention of the place in literature. A asume this is a new find, despite being so close to the village. Local

legend and toponymy of place just a few hundred meters along the road to the west, mention gallows, where death sentences were executed during the middle ages. A local church of st. Leonhard would corroborate this story. Therefore it is unlikely that buildings can be dated to the middle ages or younger period.

Conclusion

Despite lack of firm evidence I recognize these ruins as remains of roman mansio. Probably dating from the 2nd to 4th century AD. Only more detailed investigation can reveal the true nature of these buildings. But for the time being I resort to Occam's razor. Existence of roman mansio on this location is very likely and logical considering the path of roman road nearby. Size of buildings, orientation and internal division also suggest roman period buildings. Building A is probably the main building with walled court, few horse stables in the south and main building in the center. Cistern inside would provide water for pack animals, guests and staff of the mansio. Building B is probably a blacksmith's workplace. It is logical that it is detached from the main building, to prevent fire spreading to it.

Image 1: Location of building, marked with red star

Image 2: LIDAR Hillshade visualisation with marked buildings

Image 3: LIDAR SVF visualisation

Image 4: LIDAR Hillshade visualisation

Image 5: LIDAR Slope visualisation

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